

The RNA World Hypothesis: A Critical Reassessment of Prebiotic Plausibility.

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Abstract

The RNA World hypothesis proposes that self-replicating RNA preceded DNA-based life approximately 4.2 billion years ago. However, the equilibrium constant $K \approx 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$ for nucleotide condensation (derived from $\Delta G^{\circ}_{\text{hyd}} = -22.2$ kJ/mol) and conservative estimates of prebiotic nucleotide concentrations ($[N] \ll 10^{-10}$ M), suggest that not a single RNA tetranucleotide would have existed in terrestrial water through stepwise oligomerization. This derives from four critical factors: (1) ribose instability in water ($t_{1/2} \approx 300$ days at 25°C), (2) negligible prebiotic phosphate availability, (3) the endergonic nature of nucleoside phosphorylation ($\Delta G' \approx +14$ kJ·mol⁻¹), and (4) labile glycosidic bonds. Additionally, the variety of competing nucleotide isomers increases hyperexponentially with oligomer length—dinucleotides alone would exist in 57,600–360,000 structural variants. Analysis of key experimental studies reveals that high concentrations ($\approx 10^{-2}$ M) of pure, activated nucleotides under carefully controlled conditions were required to generate even short RNA oligomers—conditions that are impossibly remote prebiotically. Wet-dry cycling experiments relied on carefully timed temperature control, exclusion of interfering chemicals, and rapid cycling that would destroy reactants and products. Origin-of-life research should adopt sensitivity analysis protocols to systematically evaluate how experimental parameters extrapolate toward prebiotically plausible conditions.

Introduction

The RNA World hypothesis (RWH) remains the leading evolutionary framework for life's origin.¹ This pre-DNA period has been dated to approximately 4.2 billion years ago.² Origin-of-life (OoL) models posit violent conditions during this era, including extreme heat from massive meteor impacts and powerful oceanic tides driven by a nearby moon and Earth's rapid rotation.^{3,4,5,6}

The RWH's appeal stems from proposing that a single class of biomolecule could both catalyse reactions and carry genetic information. Conceptual details remain vague, however. OoL researchers contend that RNA chains must be at least 30–50 nucleotides (nt) long to catalyse reactions in primitive life-like systems.^{7,8} Yet nearly all in vitro RNA ribozymes—whether designed or selected from vast candidate libraries—are considerably longer. Notable examples include Voytek & Joyce (140 nt),⁹ McGinness *et al.* (165 nt),¹⁰ Johnston *et al.* (165 nt),¹¹ Bartel & Szostak (119 nt),¹² Eklund & Bartel (186),¹³ and Robertson *et al.* (60 nt).¹⁴

Other teams have developed systems capable of at least partial self-replication when supplied with necessary components: Spiegelman's Monster, Spiegelman *et al.* (218 nt)¹⁵ and Mills *et al.* (218 nt),¹⁶ Kim & Joyce (170–180 nt),¹⁷ Robertson & Joyce (170–180 nt),¹⁸ and Wochner *et al.* (>187 nt).¹⁹

It is striking that laboratory experiments typically requiring RNA exceeding 100 nt are presented as prebiotically plausible support for the RWH, given that RNA is a labile polymer prone to hydrolysis.²⁰ These experiments demanded highly specific sequences in high-concentration identical copies, often replenished by researchers to achieve desired outcomes.

This lack of chemical plausibility is widespread. Nearly half a century ago, Gish highlighted the highly speculative character of these publications.²¹

“There is no way to observe or test any postulated evolutionary origin of life. All such theories are mere postulates, all related laboratory experiments are mere exercises in organic chemistry. This has been acknowledged even by a number of prominent evolutionists.”

Without historical evidence, speculations have proliferated. As plausible scenarios were exhausted, increasingly fanciful proposals have emerged, dispersed among diverse OoL models including: iron–sulphur / surface-metabolism²², Lipid World²³, Peptide / Amyloid World²⁴, clay / mineral surface catalysis²⁵, alkaline hydrothermal-vent origin²⁶, hot-spring wet–dry cycling²⁷, Thioester World²⁸, coacervates / phase-separated droplets²⁹, autocatalytic sets / systems chemistry³⁰, ice / cold-origin³¹, formamide chemistry³², UV-driven photochemistry³³, and RNA–peptide coevolution³⁴. Since none has persuaded thoughtful scientists, proposals involving deliberate extraterrestrial intervention or accidental transport of extraterrestrial biomolecules (panspermia³⁵) have gained attention—though these sidestep the question of how life arose naturally.

Most or all models cannot be simultaneously correct, as they require mutually inconsistent chemical conditions. To avoid wasted effort, sound chemical judgment should quickly identify which experiments fail to reflect credible prebiotic environments. An obvious criterion is whether chemicals were present in sufficient concentration and purity to be relevant.

This minimal criterion is applied here to the RWH as simply as possible to demonstrate how unnecessary effort can be avoided. The fundamental question examined is: what maximum length could abiotic RNA have achieved, and at what concentration?

Length and concentration of RNA

RNA chains are produced by condensing nucleotides, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Condensation of nucleotides to form RNA polymers.

Let N represent a nucleotide such as molecule I in figure 1, having one phosphate group attached. Ignoring side-reactions for simplicity, the polymerization equilibria would be:

$$\therefore [N_2] = K_1[N]^2$$

$$\therefore [N_3] = K_2[N_2][N] = K_1K_2[N]^3$$

$$\therefore [N_4] = K_3[N_3][N] = K_1K_2K_3[N]^4$$

By induction,

$$[N_n] = K_1K_2K_3 \dots K_{n-1}[N]^n \quad (4)$$

We will assume $K \approx K_1 \approx K_2 \approx \dots \approx K_{n-1}$, leading to

$$[N_n] \approx K^{n-1}[N]^n \quad (5)$$

The simple relationship shown in eqn. (5) indicates that knowing K and $[N]$ would allow the concentration of RNA of any length to be estimated, assuming no side reactions or physical effects like entanglement that would prevent access to the oligomer ends. Only if acceptable values of K and $[N]$ existed will the RWH be credible.

Should RNA strands have arisen through extraordinary and currently unknown localized prebiotic processes, unavoidable chemical principles would have quickly both diluted and destroyed them under RWH aqueous conditions.

RNA hydrolyses rapidly

RNA hydrolyzes readily in water. While the half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of a DNA phosphodiester bond in neutral water at 25 °C is ~30 million years^{43,36,37,38} RNA bonds are far less stable due to the 2'-OH group, which enables a two-step cleavage via a 2',3'-cyclic phosphate intermediate. At pH 6–7 and 25 °C, RNA phosphodiester bonds have $t_{1/2} \approx 4$ years (uncatalysed)^{37,39,40}. Hydrolysis accelerates sharply with temperature ($t_{1/2} \approx 9$ days per bond at 100 °C³⁹), and is further enhanced under alkaline conditions or by divalent metals and mineral surfaces. Comprehensive kinetic data has been provided by Oivanen *et al.* which permits extrapolation to half-lives at other temperatures.⁴¹ Oivanen *et al.* also reported that the hydrolysis is much faster under alkaline conditions or the presence of divalent metals or mineral surfaces.

Sequence context also influences reactivity through intra- and intermolecular interactions.^{37,42}

The whole-molecule half-life (time half of molecules remain intact) can be estimated by

$$t_{\frac{1}{2},molecule} = \frac{t_{\frac{1}{2},bond}}{L-1} \quad (6)$$

as derived in Appendix 1. For example, if $L=10$

$$t_{\frac{1}{2},molecule} = \frac{t_{\frac{1}{2},bond}}{9} = \frac{4}{9} \approx 0.44 \text{ years.}$$

Free energy of hydrolysis to calculate K

The equilibrium constant K in equation (5) can be calculated from the free energy of hydrolysis, which is the reverse of the condensation reaction. A widely cited study determined $\Delta G^{\circ}_{hyd} = -22.2 \text{ kJ/mol}$ for deoxyribonucleotide hydrolysis (DNA) at 25°C and pH 7 (See figure 2).⁴³ RNA condensation yields approximately the same ΔG° value, indicating that hydrolysis is strongly favoured for both DNA and RNA.⁴⁴

Figure 2. Condensation of nucleotides is endergonic (thermodynamically unfavourable) and hydrolysis of oligomers is exergonic (thermodynamically favourable). Not drawn to exact scale.

According to the Gibbs free energy equation,

$$\Delta G^{\circ} = -RT \ln(K_{eq}) \quad (7)$$

where:

- ΔG° is the standard Gibbs free Energy change.
- R is the ideal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J/mol} \cdot \text{K}$).
- T is the absolute temperature 298.15 K (i.e. 25°C) for standard conditions.
- K_{eq} is the equilibrium constant for the reaction $N_{n-1} + N \rightleftharpoons N_n$.

K_1 for the condensation reaction in eqn. (1) is found to be:

$$K_{eq} = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G^{\circ}}{RT}\right) \quad (8)$$

Since $\Delta G^{\circ} = +22.2 \text{ kJ/mol} = +22,200 \text{ J/mol}$,

and $RT = 8.314 \cdot 298.15 \approx 2,478.82 \text{ J/mol}$

$$K_{eq} = \exp(-8.9559) \approx \mathbf{0.000129} \quad (9)$$

Concentration of nucleotides (nucleoside monophosphates, NMPs)

Since reasonable values for K at different temperatures can be estimated for eqn. (5), a fundamental question for the RWH becomes: what values of $[N]$ should be assumed? The total mass balance must hold, with total nucleotide distributed across oligomers plus unreacted monomer:

$$[N]_{\text{total}} = [N] + 2[N_2] + 3[N_3] + \dots + n[N_n] \quad (10)$$

Since at equilibrium

$$K_{n-1} = \frac{[N_n]}{[N_{n-1}][N]}, \quad (11)$$

it follows that

$$\frac{[N_n]}{[N_{n-1}]} = K_{n-1}[N] \quad (12)$$

Since from eqn. (10) $K_{n-1} \approx 10^{-4}$, and under abiotic condition $[N] \ll 1$, eqn. (12) confirms that $[N_n] \ll [N_{n-1}]$ for all values of n . This means that very little of the initial nucleotide is consumed to form the oligomers. At equilibrium, when maximum oligomer concentration has been achieved:

$$[N_{\text{eq}}] \approx [N_{\text{initial}}] \quad (13)$$

The RWH is only feasible if $[N_{\text{eq}}]$ is very high, which this paper will evaluate carefully. The process begins by deconstructing the monomers used to build RNA, as shown in figure 3. This reveals that nucleotides are composed of three independent building blocks.

Figure 3. Deconstruction of nucleotides into their chemical building blocks.

A chemically sensible retrosynthetic analysis to form nucleotides is shown in figure 4, reasoning from the product backwards via steps 1→2→3. This approach begins by constructing sugar ribose and each nucleobase independently, then connecting them through a glycosylation bond in step 1. A phosphate group must then be added at the hydroxyl group at the 5'-hydroxyl position of the resulting nucleosides. This analysis reveals 4 reasons why $[N_{\text{eq}}]$ could only have been present in trace amounts.

Figure 4. Retrosynthetic analysis to form nucleotides from (D)-ribose and nucleobases.

1. Abiotic synthesis of the ribose sugar problematic

Next, reasonable prebiotic concentrations for the individual molecules used to construct nucleotides must be estimated. The Formose reaction is considered the most promising route to synthesize ribose, although at prebiotically realistic concentrations of formaldehyde ($<10^{-3}$ M), no sugar products have been observed (far less ribose) even after adding minerals and salts.^{45,46,47} Yadav *et al.* summarized their extensive review of the literature on these experiments euphemistically stating that,⁴⁵

"Most of the above variations of formose reactions still deal with formaldehyde as the main starting molecule, but a selective *plausible prebiotic pathway to ribose remains elusive.*" (Emphasis added)

If some ribose had formed prebiotically, it is very unstable in water, with half-lives calculated to be 73 minutes at pH 7.0 and 100 °C, 300 days at 25 °C pH 7.4 and ~44 years at pH 7.0 and 0 °C according to OoL specialists Larralde *et al.*⁴⁸ These researchers did not identify the degradation products given the huge variety produced. They concluded that⁴⁸

"The above results show that stability considerations preclude the use of ribose and other sugars as prebiotic reagents except under very special conditions. It follows that *ribose and other sugars were not components of the first genetic material.*" (Emphasis added)

2. Abiotic synthesis of nucleobases problematic

The HCN tar-like polymer has been considered the most promising source of prebiotic nucleobases.⁵² Miller examined the equilibrium steady state concentration of HCN as a function of temperature and pH values and found it to be 6×10^{-16} M at 200 °C and pH 8; 7×10^{-13} M at 100 °C (pH 8); and 2×10^{-6} M at 0 °C (pH 8). This is several orders of magnitude lower than known to be needed to produce nucleobases at detectable levels.⁴⁹

Nevertheless, most of the experiments to form adenine, arguably the most commonly synthesized nucleobase for OoL studies, use very high concentration of HCN (1.0–11.0 M). High concentration of HCN generates polymeric material called azulmin. Consequently, the usefulness of HCN, to produce nucleobases has been viewed critically.⁵²

Several chemical requirements must be fulfilled for step 2 in figure 4 to obtain a properly attached nucleobase to ribose via a glycosidic bond.

- Only the five-membered ribose (furanose sugar) must be used despite the many alternative sugars also present, including the thermodynamically more favorable six-membered ring pyranose.
- Many five-membered sugar isomers would have formed, but only (D)-ribose must be used.
- The nucleobase must be attached at only the N-9 position of the purines and the N-1 position of the pyrimidines. All the N-glycosidic bonds must form the β and not α stereoisomers at the (1')-position of the ribose. This is discussed in the next section.

Furthermore, much attention has been drawn to the instability of one of the nucleotides, cytosine. Cytosine is consumed by deamination (activation energy 26–29 kcal/mol) to form uracil with a half-life of ~340 years at 25°C and pH 7 (excluding all chemicals that catalyse this reaction).⁵⁰ Other destructive reactions would also have occurred, in particular due solar UV light that would have quickly converted cytosine to its photohydrate and to cyclobutane photodimers.⁵⁰ Cytosine has not been identified on meteorites nor is it produced by electric spark discharge experiments. Since cytosine base-pairs with guanine in DNA, the unavailability of cytosine implies guanine would also not be usable if the RNA World evolved into the extant DNA genetic code.

Shapiro has also vigorously critiqued the variety of inconsistent conditions used to synthesis the individual biological nucleobases.⁵¹

3. Abiotic N-glycosylation problematic

An N-glycosidic bond must be formed at the C2'-OH position to link ribose with a nucleobase. The half-life of this bond is about 6,000 years but decreases rapidly with temperature. Some values were calculated using parameters from Stockbridge *et al.*²⁰, see Table 1 in Appendix 2.

A productive abiotic pathway for the required N-glycosylation step has never been found despite years of intensive research, due to the high-temperature and other destructive conditions required.⁵² The high activation energy destroyed the reactants and leads to undesired side products. This is known as the *nucleosidation problem*.⁴⁴ After considerable experimentation and optimization, Orgel succeed in obtaining up to 3% yields of the β -adenosine^{53,54} but N-glycosylation of the pyrimidine nucleosides (cytidine and uridine) under the same reaction conditions did not occur,^{53,54,55} precluding ever forming relevant RNA.

4. Abiotic 5'-phosphorylation problematic

In step 3 (Figure 4), nucleosides must be phosphorylated at the 5'-OH position. The reaction Adenosine + Pi \rightarrow AMP is endergonic (i.e., unfavourable), with $\Delta G' \approx +14 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ at 25 °C and pH 7.^{56,57} An extensive study by Costanzo *et al.* examined the chemical challenges of introducing phosphodiester bonds prebiotically.⁵⁸ Earth formation models predict virtually all phosphorus would have been inaccessible as water-insoluble minerals such as apatites. Note orthophosphate is precipitated by divalent metals such as Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ and thus not available for reaction in solution.⁵⁹ Costanzo *et al.* tested 12 phosphate minerals to determine which could phosphorylate nucleosides.

Crystal minerals were ground to fine powder (to increase reactivity) and suspended in pure formamide, an ideal experimental solvent. Formamide (HCONH₂) hydrolyzes readily in water to form formic acid and ammonia, making it implausible as a prebiotic solvent. Nevertheless, suspensions were heated to 130°C for 72 h and centrifuged, carefully excluding all water. Adenosine concentrations of 0.025 M were used (roughly a level teaspoon of granulated sugar in half a litre of water⁶⁰ with the formamide temperature lowered to 90°C before adding adenosine.

At 90°C in water, no adenosine phosphorylation occurred and the glycosidic bond degraded. Therefore, formamide was used as solvent in nearly all experiments. Reactions were terminated when degradation products became dominant (figure 5). The highest 5'-AMP yield (~6% of input adenosine) resulted from pure libethenite, Cu₂(PO₄)(OH). Five minerals produced no phosphorylation products, two produced trace amounts, and the remainder yielded far less than 1%.

Figure 5. Adenosine phosphorylation in formamide at 90 °C in Reichenbachite, Cu²⁺₅(PO₄)₂(OH)₄. Mineral pretreated for 72 hours at 130 °C. From Costanzo *et al.* slightly modified.⁵⁸

The maximum ~6% yield (moles of product per mole of input adenosine) was only achievable through expert interventions such as grinding to increase surface area and pretreating at 130°C in dry formamide. Leaving reactants at 90°C for several weeks would have destroyed the phosphorylated product. Other laboratory procedures for phosphorylating riboses have been reported. Gibard *et al.* succeeded in forming oligouridine tetramers in one pot, starting from nucleosides reacted with the phosphorylating agent diamidophosphate (DAP) at high concentration.⁶¹ DAP does not form spontaneously from dissolved orthophosphate + ammonia in bulk water, and its hydrolysis is exergonic.⁵⁹ Nevertheless, Gibard *et al.* used very high DAP proportions: 1 equivalent of nucleoside mixed with 5 equivalents DAP, 5 equivalents of the activating agent imidazole, and approximately 2 drops of D₂O, ground into a paste (Supplementary Information Method C, page 5)⁶¹. During the reaction, the paste-reaction was further ground for 5 min daily at room temperature.

The four chemical details just discussed demonstrate that realistically, virtually no ribose present would have been phosphorylated at any point under prebiotic conditions.

In cells, elaborate metabolic biochemical pathways involving special enzymes produce nucleotides but these processes have not inspired relevant abiotic counterparts. As Yadav *et al.* diplomatically summarized these attempts,⁵²

“So far, all attempts to recapitulate the biological pathways for nucleotide synthesis (or other chemistries) have at best produced dubious results.”

2':3'-cyclic AMP instead of phosphorylated AMP

Since thermodynamics favours hydrolysis instead of condensation of the nucleotides shown in figure 4, researchers often study 2':3'-cyclic AMP instead. This is because its strained cyclic phosphate is in a high-energy state that can polymerize more readily to form RNA-like chains (i.e., with mixed 2'–5' and 3'–5' linkages).^{62,63,64}

When Costanzo *et al.* reacted adenosine with dissolved KH_2PO_4 (0.05 M at 90 °C), 2':3'-cyclic AMP was only obtained in dry formamide solvent.⁵⁸ However, virtually no KH_2PO_4 would have been available prebiotically, since the dominant natural phosphorus reservoir would have been apatite-group minerals (e.g., fluorapatite, hydroxylapatite), which are highly insoluble in water.⁵⁸

Oceanic concentration of prebiotic nucleotides

According to figure 4, forming nucleotides depends on the availability of the nucleobases, ribose, phosphate, plus successful attachment of nucleobase to ribose at the C1'–OH position plus successful attachment of phosphate to the ribose at the C5'–OH position. The analysis in the sections above implies that only trace concentrations of the four nucleotides would have been present in water at thermodynamic equilibrium. Since our approach to considering the plausibility of the RWH is to minimize effort, exact concentrations are unnecessary. The generous assumptions can serve as a baseline from which quantitative plausibility can be further refined.

Bada calculated that a maximum concentration of all amino acids in oceans would have been about 10^{-10} M by estimating the rate of influx all extra-terrestrial amino acids minus the rate of their degradation.⁶⁵ It is reasonable to assume that at equilibrium in prebiotic water the average concentration of the nucleotides (including the missing cytosine monophosphate) would have been $[N] \ll 10^{-10}$ M.

Using this value and $K \approx 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$ from (9) in eqn. (5) leads to

$$[N_{n=4}] \approx 1.3 \times 10^{(-4)3} \times 10^{(-10)4} \approx 10^{-52} \text{ M} \quad (14)$$

To put this into perspective, we can calculate the molarity resulting in 1 molecule in all terrestrial water. There is about 1.26×10^{21} L water on earth. Using Avogadro's number for the number of molecules in 1 mole, the molarity that contains 1 RNA molecule is:

$$M = \frac{1}{(6.022 \times 10^{23}) \times (1.26 \times 10^{21})} = 1.3 \times 10^{-45} \text{ M} \quad (15)$$

Since $10^{-52} \text{ M} \ll 10^{-45} \text{ M}$ we conclude that no RNA four nucleotides or longer would have existed in terrestrial water prebiotically. It is ironic that most students are taught that life arose in a primordial ocean, despite water being a formidable impediment to form biomolecules such as RNA.

The only way OoL researchers can obtain much longer RNA oligomers is to envision special conditions that dramatically increase the values of K and $[N]$. These proposals will be examined below, but first an important topic will be addressed that must not be overlooked.

Variety of mononucleotide isomers

Critiques of OoL publications have emphasized the variety of chemicals that would have formed using the standard OoL synthetic routes, starting with molecules such as formaldehyde, hydrogen cyanide, and amino acids. These products, plus the multitude of amines, aldehydes, alcohols, and carboxylic acids also present in the environment would have interfered with producing RNA and DNA.

Neglecting these realities, professor Tan considered a hypothetical ideal starting point involving only the canonical furanose sugar; the 4 correct nucleobases adenine, cytosine, guanine, and uracil; and phosphate.⁶⁶ All chemicals inevitably present were excluded in her analysis, including the more stable 6-membered isomers furanose can isomerize into.⁶⁶ What fraction of the nucleotide monomers would have had the requisite β -D-ribofuranose, N9-glycosidic bond for purines/N1 for pyrimidines, and 3',5'-phosphodiester linkages? She pointed out that

- Ribose exists in 5 interconverting isomers in aqueous solution.
- Each of these isomers have 4 hydroxyl ($-OH$) groups that could form a glycosidic (C–N) bonds with a nucleobase or phosphate.
- Adenine and cytosine have 3 $-NH$ groups able to form glycosidic (C–N) bonds (adenine and cytosine exist in two equilibrating forms in water).
- Guanine has five NH groups and uracil has 2 $-NH$ groups where glycosidic bonds could form.
- After glycosidic bonds formed, 3 $-OH$ positions would remain where a phosphate could attach.

Therefore, the number of possible isomers that can form would be:

$$AMP = 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 3 = 180 \quad (16)$$

$$CMP = 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 3 = 180 \quad (17)$$

$$GMP = 5 \times 4 \times 5 \times 3 = 300 \quad (18)$$

$$UMP = 5 \times 4 \times 2 \times 3 = 120 \quad (19)$$

This analysis assumes ideal stoichiometries of reactants, and neglects many other isomers that would have formed, namely having zero to multiple phosphates or bases attached to the same sugar. Also, all possible cyclic products, including polyphosphates, were not taken into account. Consequently, Tan's approach matches ours, namely, to provide overly generous assumptions evolutionists would be willing to accept as a baseline for discussion.

The $[N] = 10^{-10}$ M assumed in eqn. (14) refers to only the single correct nucleotide used to form RNA, so when the competing isomers are also taken into account this represents a generously "high" prebiotic assumption. The large variety of isomers able to interfere with the 'correct' ribose has important consequences when evaluating OoL experiments, as will be discussed next.

Number of dinucleotide isomers formed prebiotically

Tan also pointed out that after one nucleobase and one phosphate have attached to the ribose, two of the four –OH groups remain on the ribose (for each of the above competing isomers!) through which dinucleotides could form using a diphosphate bond, leading to 4 isomeric variants.⁶⁶ Altogether, these alternative bond locations lead to $180 \times 180 \times 4 = 129,600$ possible AC (adenine-cytosine ribose dinucleotide) alternatives. The DNA complementary UG dinucleotide would be present in $120 \times 300 \times 4 = 144,000$ variants. The lowest number of dinucleotide isomers results from two UMP to produce $120 \times 120 \times 4 = 57,600$ isomers, and the highest when linking two GMP to form $300 \times 300 \times 4 = 360,000$ isomers. Converting the monomer into a dimer increased the variety of isomers by about 3 orders of magnitude!

The hyperexponential increase in oligomeric isomers with length has a profound effect on how OoL experiments must be designed. Clearly, increasing the oligomer chain rapidly ‘dilutes’ the proportion of correctly linked isomers to irrelevant levels no matter how concentrated the original mixture of nucleotides. Special reaction conditions can be selected to favour the desired product, but producing RNA oligomers successfully requires using pure single-isomer nucleotides. Interfering chemicals, including isomers, must be rigorously excluded.

RNA as an information carrier

Before examining key OoL experiments to see how the values of K and $[N]$ used in eqn. (5) were optimised by experiment design, it seems worthwhile to mention why only pure nucleotide isomers must be used if RNA is to serve a DNA precursor information carrier.

Tan pointed out that 129,600 possible 5'-AC-3' dinucleotides isomers could form, and the complementary strand 5'-GU-3' would have had 144,000 possible isomers. However, due to inadequate base-pairing constraints about 72,000 of the double-stranded dinucleotides may be considered viable. Therefore, if an RNA duplex had served as an information carrier, this 2-nucleotide region alone would have been present in about $129,600 \times 72,000 = 9,331,200,000$ variant base pairs.⁶⁶

This reality can be combined with the claim by Robertson and Joyce that if a replication fidelity of about 99% could have been achieved, an RNA genome length of about 100 nucleotides might be theoretically possible.⁸⁰ This claim refers to replicating a sequence based on only 4 nucleotide options. It overlooks the incomprehensibly large number of possible polymeric isomers of that length. Furthermore, it is inconceivable that genetic instructions could have been reliably decoded in some manner from such an irregular medium. In addition, no OoL experiments have addressed the challenge of replicating a specific sequence of hundreds of potential isomers 100 times in a row.

In contrast, the current organism believed to have the shortest genome for a free-living, non-parasitic organism is that of *Pelagibacter ubique*, which ~1.3 million base pairs and encodes around 1,354 protein-coding genes and 35 RNA genes.^{67,68} That is over 1 million nucleotides linked only by the single, correct isomer. Therefore, the RWH proponents cannot plausibly claim that RNA strands a few nucleotides long at best could have served as an information carrier that was transformed into DNA, able to code for protein sequences.

Ignoring irrelevant studies

Continuing in the spirit of judging the plausibility of the RWH as efficiently as possible, it is sensible to quickly discard publications having no merit. Those new to the field need to be aware that a disturbing number of publications that claimed dramatic effects were retracted later, as searches using ChatGPT show. Some were even published in *Nature*, the world's most prestigious journal by professors from elite universities.⁶⁹

Key studies often provide overstated claims in the summaries and throughout the text, but examining the experimental details usually reveals no prebiotic relevance. A few examples will be provided to illustrate.

One common issue involves irrelevant laboratory solvents, used to avoid degradation in water. For example, Ferris *et al.*⁷⁰ tested cyanate with cyanoacetylene to produce cytosine using *dimethylformamide* as the solvent, carefully excluding water, since cyanate and cyanoacetylene both hydrolyze easily.

Yamada heated formamide at 170–190 °C to produce purines, including adenine.⁷¹ However, the high temperature reaction condition needed would have decomposed formamide to ammonia and carbon dioxide. The general principle is that when unrealistic high temperatures are used the experiments are terminated very quickly.

Lagoja and Herdewijn developed a process to form adenine by reacting glycinamide and diformylurea at 175 °C to form hypoxanthine.⁷² The best drying agent P₂O₅ was then used despite being prebiotically implausible at high concentration and processed *at the much lower temperature* of 100 °C followed by some reactions at 100 °C to produce adenine.

Burcar *et al.* used a prebiotically irrelevant laboratory condensing agent, 1-ethyl-3-(3-(dimethylamino)propyl) carbodiimide (EDC) with imidazole to activate nucleotide condensation.⁷³

In most experiments the yields were irrelevantly low despite prebiotically unreasonable optimizations. Miller, Bada, and others froze solutions (prepared 0.1 M NH₄CN from gaseous HCN and NH₃ and froze the solutions at -20 °C for 25 yrs.^{49,74,75} Only trace amounts of adenine and guanine of the biological nucleobases were detected, suggesting that almost only a cyanide polymer was formed. Only after centrifugation and hydrolysis with 6.0 N HCl at 100 °C was 0.038% adenine and 0.0035% guanine obtained, a very modest result.

In other experiments, Schwartz *et al.* used 0.01M HCN solutions with ammonium hydroxide at pH 9.2 at 25 °C to obtain 0.004% of adenine.⁷⁶

Skilled chemists can disregard most of the publications devoted to form RNA prebiotically with little effort.

Increasing the equilibrium constant K via activating phosphates

For thermodynamic reasons, the nucleotides shown in figure 4 do not oligomerize sufficiently for the RWH to be credible. Therefore, OoL researchers use a series of chemical principles (conversion with activation groups, templating, concentration by compartmentalization, etc.) to increase their reactivity.

Phosphorimidazolides, shown in figure 6, are often used to activate nucleotides to facilitate oligomerization.^{77,78,79} However, the relevance of ribonucleoside phosphorimidazolides prebiotically has met with considerable skepticism.⁴⁴ Furthermore, only very short linear

(plus cyclic) oligomers formed using these activated monomers. The favoured products are the 5',5'-pyrophosphates, followed by the 2,5'- phosphodiester linkage and, last, the biologically relevant 3',5'- linked.⁸⁰

Figure 6. Proposed abiotic synthetic routes to nucleoside-5'-phosphorimidazolides by (A) Yi *et al.*⁷⁹ and (B) Mariana *et al.*⁸¹

Some metal ions including Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Lu^{3+} improved the imidazole-activated polymerization, leading to maximum chain lengths of 5-mer, 4-mer, and 3-mer, respectively.^{82,83,84} However, as mentioned above orthophosphate is precipitated by divalent metals.⁵⁹

High concentrations of other external activating agents such as cyanamide,⁸⁵ and carbodiimides⁸⁶ have been employed to polymerize nucleotides in aqueous solution. These would have quickly hydrolyzed in water and in any event could not form oligomers longer than dinucleotides dimers in sustainable yields.⁴⁴

Much attention has been devoted to the used of various minerals as potential concentrating environments for RNA precursors, in particular Montmorillonite, discussed in Appendix 3.

All the above attempts to increase the equilibrium constant K must inevitably lower the concentration of the (activated) prebiotic nucleotide. As pointed out by OoL specialist Ferris,²⁵

"the prebiotic conversion of the 5'-phosphorylated nucleotide to an activated nucleotide under prebiotic conditions has not been accomplished at the time of writing."

Very little of any nucleotide would have been activated, since two or more water-unstable reactants must be co-localized in very high concentrations and ideal stoichiometry, whereby the product is also unstable in water. Prebiotically,

$$[N] \ll [N_{act}] \quad (20)$$

where N_{act} is the chemically converted nucleotide optimised to undergo oligomerization. To emphasize the magnitude of what eqn. (20) expresses, the commonly used activating or coupling agents used, such as EDAC (1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide), would not have been present prebiotically. (EDAC is used in the Montmorillonite studies, see Appendix 3)

Rearranging eqn (5) that is based on non-activated nucleotide,

$$[N_n] \approx K^{n-1}[N]^n \quad (21)$$

When the same oligomers use activated nucleotides, the relationship would be:

$$[N_n] \approx K_{act}^{n-1} [N_{act}]^n \quad (22)$$

Although the equilibrium constant would be improved, the significantly lower concentration of N_{act} would likely yield less of the oligomer, since

$$K^{n-1} [N]^n > K_{act}^{n-1} [N_{act}]^n \quad (23)$$

To illustrate, suppose activation increased K by a factor of 10^4 , but only 10^{-3} of N would be converted to N_{act} . For the reaction,

these assumptions lead to

$$[N_2] = K_1 [N]^2 > K_{1act} [N_{act}]^2 = 10^4 K_1 \times (10^{-3})^2 [N]^2 \quad (25)$$

which equals $10^{-2} K_1 [N]^2$.

Increasing K and $[N]$ using wet-dry cycles

Higher equilibrium constants can be obtained by removing water, including that produced from nucleotide condensation. This is achieved using wet-dry cycles (also called concentration-evaporation, dehydration-rehydration, or drying-wetting cycles), which also concentrate nucleotides locally.

Representative studies illustrate key principles. Hassenkam and Deamer placed drops of AMP + UMP and GMP + UMP aqueous mixtures (10 mM, pH 3) on freshly cleaved mica surfaces and evaporated water on a hot plate at 80°C.⁸⁷ Initial drying took several minutes, then dried samples were maintained at 80°C for 30 min before rehydration with minimal ultra-pure deionized water. After three wet-dry cycles, mica surfaces were washed with Milli-Q water and dried under nitrogen gas. Material adhering to mica included large polymeric cyclic and linear substances. Room-temperature experiments produced no polymeric material.

Song *et al.* prepared aqueous AMP solutions (10 mM, pH 2.5) at room temperature, transferred small volumes into wells on glass slides, and dried them on a thermostat-controlled hot plate at 85°C.⁸⁸ After drying (several minutes), slides were maintained at 85°C for ~30 min to provide activation energy for condensation, producing a thin film. Water was then added at room temperature and stirred for ~5 seconds with a spatula. This process was repeated for exactly 3 wet-dry cycles. The authors identified a broad oligomer distribution: for UMP_n, the average was $n = 16.3 \pm 10.5$ with maximum $n = 53$; for AMP_n, average $n = 14.7 \pm 9.3$ with longest oligomer $n = 44$ (their Fig. 2).⁸⁸ As expected, larger oligomer yields increased from 1 to 2 wet-dry cycles but decreased dramatically with the third cycle, especially for the largest oligomers (their Fig. 2).⁸⁸

These carefully designed wet-dry experiments produce favorable equilibrium constants (by driving off water) and concentrate nucleotides in two-dimensional regions. For example, Hassenkam and Deamer estimated that evaporating a 20–40 μL drop of 10 mM nucleotide solution over 1 cm² produced 10–30 nm thick films composed of 30–60 *stacked pure nucleotides*.⁸⁷ (Note that UV radiation would have degraded dry prebiotic oligomers no longer protected by deep water.)

In bulk water, H^+ and OH^- ions are randomly distributed, but at hydrophobic interfaces such as air or solid surfaces, high H^+ concentrations can form.⁸⁸ These protons accelerate condensation via acid-catalysed mechanisms by activating phosphate groups for nucleophilic attack by free ribose -OH groups.⁸⁸ Additionally, electric fields at interfaces help align nucleotides and further facilitate reactions.⁸⁸

Importantly, tightly packed nucleotides attached to glass surfaces are protected from moisture. Furthermore, proper alignment during evaporation can occur, analogous to crystallization. Crucially, once solid thin films form, dried nucleotides become immobilized and cannot polymerize further. This is why experimental designs required adding minimal water after the condensation step, which was then quickly evaporated.

Song *et al.* admitted that under their experimental conditions the RNA polymers would be completely degraded to the component nucleotides within a few days and required careful experimental design.^{42,88} This is corroborated by the work of Mungi *et al.* who reported that about half of AMP solutions are depurinated (i.e., the N-glycosidic bond is broken) within **~6 hours** under representative reaction conditions used for dehydration-rehydration experiments (~pH 2 and 90 °C).⁸⁹ Glycosidic bonds are known to be very labile, especially in purines⁹⁰ and the rate of depurination accelerates rapidly at >85 °C.⁹¹

Earlier studies had demonstrated the feasibility of synthesizing RNA and DNA oligomers at 70–90 °C.⁹² Consequently, ideal temperatures and pH values to form phosphodiester bonds were selected for wet-dry experiments despite the rapid destruction of the starting nucleotides and the oligomers. The laboratory conditions needed to capitalize on short-term kinetic trade-offs. Song *et al.* suggested that loss of the N-glycosidic bond may not have been significant enough to ruin their experiments despite the results reported by Mungi *et al.* due to the very small differences in conditions: Song *et al.* used 85 °C, pH = 2.5, 10 mM AMP whereas Mungi *et al.* used 90 °C, pH = 2.0, 2.5 mM AMP.^{88,88}

Several factors optimised oligomerization:

- High initial concentration of nucleotides.
- The absence of other reactants.
- Ideal and constant temperatures.
- Removal of the oligomer products from the heat source.
- Very short exposure time to temperatures ca. 85 °C.

These experiments are claimed to simulate prebiotic nucleotide oligomerization in freshwater environments in the vicinity of volcanos, whereas ideal laboratory conditions were selected.

A wide range of hot spring conditions would have been present, having pH \approx 1– 7 and fluctuating temperature \approx 25–100 °C. Salts from sea water would have interfered with forming pure films of nucleotides, further limiting the environmental requirements.

Shapiro critiqued models based on the dry-lagoon concept, pointing out that decomposition and side reactions caused by the drying process cannot be ignored.⁵⁰

Discussion

When evaluating OoL models like the RWH, a productive strategy is to discard publications that don't merit further scrutiny. Eqn. (5) provides useful guidance, suggesting that at around

25 °C not a single RNA tetranucleotide would have been present in terrestrial water, produced through step-wise oligomerization. Since RNA diesterphosphate bonds hydrolyse rapidly, oligomers produced under exceptional conditions would have rapidly hydrolysed upon contacting water.

A sensible starting point when first viewing a paper on the RWH is to determine what concentration of pure nucleotide was used in the experiments. From the work of Tan, 57,600–360,000 dinucleotide isomers can form assuming only ribose, phosphate, and nucleobase react together, of which only 1 corresponds to RNA. This does not include the ribose containing multiple phosphates or nucleobases. Critically, the variety of possible isomers increase hyper-exponentially with oligomer length. Therefore, the important question is what purity of nucleotides or activated nucleotides was used.

Figures 1 and 3 show how nucleotides are assembled and the chemical analysis above demonstrates that nucleotides could not have accumulated in high concentrations prebiotically. Ribose decompose rapidly in water,⁴⁸ free reactive phosphate would not have been available,⁵⁸ attachment of phosphate to the C5'-OH is endergonic, the glycosidic bond is easily hydrolyzed,⁸⁹ the usual OoL synthetic routes to ribose requires unrealistic concentrations of formaldehyde and produces miniscule yields^{45,46,47} (plus a myriad of side-products) and the best OoL routes to nucleobases require unrealistic concentrations of HCN with miniscule yields, flooded with polymeric tar.^{49,74,75,76} Very low temperatures would be used to form ribose and nucleobases, whereas very high temperatures in wet-dry cycles, conditions that would have prevented accumulation of nucleotides. Another inconsistent trade-off is the pH selected for specific experiments.

Arguably, no nucleotides would have formed prebiotically at all, in stark contrast to the typical concentrations of $\sim 10^{-2}$ M at 85 °C used in the key wet-dry laboratory cycle studies⁸⁸. Despite the complex conditions to form nucleotides, all impurities were inevitably avoided, and the nucleotides were located on an ideal flat surface where they were concentrated by evaporation to $\sim 100\%$ purity.

Compounding the lack of plausibility, most current RWH experiments chemically modify nucleotides under anhydrous conditions. Even if a minute proportion of nucleotides would be activated, they would have remained entombed in dry minerals, subject to fierce destructive UV radiation, and served no role in the origin of life; or the activated nucleotides would have been quickly hydrolysed. Therefore, the wet-dry cycle experiments offer little support for the RWH.

Experiments on minerals such as Montmorillonite used concentrations of $\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-2}$ M⁹³ *activated* nucleotides precisely co-localized with optimally prepared pure Montmorillonite. This concentration corresponds to more than half a teaspoon of pure table sugar in half a litre of water where assuredly not a single activated nucleotide molecule would have been present in half-a litre.⁶⁰ Suppose a large lake isolated from sea-water had evaporated and concentrated activated nucleotide. These activated nucleotides would have been widely dispersed in a muddy or cement-like mass of chemicals, immobile and isolated from each other. Pristine flat surfaces would not have been available where all the available nucleotides could form flat films of pure activated nucleotides that excluded moisture.

Individual RWH papers could be extensively critiqued in detail on the basis of their deliberate goal-directed steps. For example, the consequences of high temperature conditions to drive condensation would have prevented any of the labile components such as ribose from forming, or surviving, prebiotically.⁴⁸ The lack of prebiotic plausibility is an open secret in the OoL community. Chemistry professor Krishnamurthy at the Scripps Research Institute has devoted his career to origin of life organic reactions and methodologies.⁹⁴ In the Special Issue: Chemical Evolution and the Origins of Life sponsored by Chemical Reviews he cautioned that⁵²

"while many of the chemistries of abiotic nucleotide synthesis are successful in producing high amounts of the products, the experimental set up is not widely accepted as prebiotically realistic in terms of its concentrations, spatial-sequence separation and the availability of pure starting materials."

In the spirit of investing time wisely, those interested in the OoL literature are well-advised to learn how to quickly separate the wheat from the chaff.

Sensitivity analysis of the reported outcomes

We have a proposal for the OoL community. It is related to the sensitivity analysis performed routinely by chemists and chemical engineers when designing chemical production processes; the range of reaction parameters must be determined that can produce products that meet target specifications.

OoL researchers inevitably test key parameters to optimize yields to ensure papers be worth publishing. Key parameters are varied to identify the best settings. Our proposal is to vary parameters to permit extrapolation towards prebiotically credible settings. It is not apparent why something so obvious is not standard practice in the OoL chemical literature. Best practice is to use DOE (Design of Experiments) methodologies that calculate the optimal parameter values for a series of experiments to provide maximum information. The resulting datasets are ideal to develop predictive equations which could potentially identify how to obtain better results.

Non-DOE experiments could easily be carried out and should even be mandatory for OoL publications for proof-of-relevance purposes. Individual parameters should be varied, such as temperature, concentration, time duration, purity, proportion of activated nucleotides, etc. Prohibitively long experiments to mimic plausible prebiotic conditions are not necessary, only enough data points to establish a trend, as illustrated in figure 7.

Figure 7. Possible outcomes of extending a reaction parameter. A: Yields rapidly approach zero when continuing the experiment for a short time. B: Yields rapidly approach zero after

systematically lowering the concentrations slightly C: Raising the temperature only slightly would decrease the yield dramatically.

Here are some experiments which should be carried out in the context of RWH studies.

- Repeat the wet-dry cycles 10, 20, and 30 more cycles.
- Repeat condensation experiments on Montmorillonite over a range of 0%–100% activated nucleotide.
- In oligomerization reactions mix the nucleotide in a range of competing isomer proportions.
- In oligomerization reactions vary the pH and temperature. (These will fluctuate naturally in nature. An ideal temperature of 85 °C would be accompanied by periods of destructive temperatures at 100 °C),
- Vary all key concentrations over a range of values.
- Place the nucleotides or activated nucleotides at optimal concentrations (e.g., 15 mM) and temperature (e.g. 85 °C) in a laboratory flask for 1, 2, 5, 10 weeks at 85 °C before performing 3 wet-dry cycles.

OoL specialists are often quite candid about OoL research when communication with other scientists. In an extensive review of studies to form nucleotides prebiotically that included 315 references, Yadav *et al.* emphasized that,

“The concentration of reactants, the formation of products in discrete steps, and the need for a specific sequence has been raised as issues that need to be addressed within the context of the early Earth environment, an effort that is ongoing. It must be pointed out that such criticisms are not unique to this work but common to almost all of the synthetic work covered in this review.”⁵²

Yadav *et al.* use the expression *to channel* to describe how outcomes were deliberately guided. For example, they wrote,⁵²

“Considering all these problems, intensive efforts have been expended in simplifying and “cleaning-up” the classical formose reaction and *to channel* it toward ribose production.” (Emphasis added)

These authors reminded the OoL community that,⁵²

“To date there has been no single prebiotically plausible experiment that has moved beyond the generation of a mixture of chemical products, infamously called “the prebiotic clutter”. And this is particularly evident in the “three pillars” of prebiotic chemistry, the Butlerow’s formose reaction, the Miller–Urey spark discharge experiment, and the Oro’s HCN polymerization reaction—even though all of them have been (and are being) studied intensively.

After a career devoted to OoL chemistry, Ferris also stated unmistakably that²⁵

"The direct formation of RNA by prebiotic processes is controversial. As will be outlined subsequently, there are *no plausible prebiotic syntheses of RNA monomers* so that many scientists in this field feel that the spontaneous formation of such complicated structures is very unlikely to have occurred on the primitive Earth."(Emphasis added)

Conclusion: No RNA implies no RNA World

The key role played by ribosomal RNAs (rRNAs) in extant cells has been offered as the strongest evidence for the RWH.^{80,95,96} The use of tRNAs in the genetic code is also claimed to be evidence that supports the hypothesis.^{1,96}

Large-scale genome surveys show that in ~95–96% of bacterial genomes the 6S, 23S and 5S rRNA genes are transcribed from a single *rrn* operon, with only a small fraction showing exclusively unlinked rRNA genes (~3.7%) or mixed arrangements (~0.6%).^{97,98}

The primary RNA transcript generally has a similar structure⁹⁹: leader sequences (~115 nt), 16S rRNA (~1,540 nt),¹⁰⁰ internal spacer with tRNA genes, 23S rRNA (~2,900 nt),⁹⁹ internal spacer 5S rRNA (~120 nt),¹⁰¹ trailer sequence.⁹⁹ The single, long primary transcript is then enzymatically cleaved by RNase III^{102,103,104}. In model bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* the full-length primary transcript precursor contains about 5,200 nucleotides.¹⁰⁴

This length poses serious problems for the RWH that claims rRNAs and tRNAs are remnants of the RNA world. Additional RNA would have been required for the full complement of tRNAs, RNA gene regulation, and a wide variety of ribozymes, requiring putative RNA genomes to have had to be at least 10,000 nucleotides. The sequences would need to be very exact and able to replicate. Our analysis has suggested, however, that not a single RNA oligomer of length 4 would have been present in water where the RWH would have existed. Furthermore, Robertson and Joyce have estimated an upper limit of about 100 nucleotides based on the inability of RNA to replicate reliably without highly-effective protein error-correcting enzymes.⁸⁰

Finally, no proposals have been offered how error-prone, labile RNA genomes in a violent early Earth could have been transformed into DNA-based organism at least 1 million base pairs long^{67,68} functioning by entirely different principles, i.e., the genetic code to produce proteins. Scientific evidence for the RWH is missing and the hypothesis contradicts fundamental chemical principles.

Appendix 1. Time RNA and DNA survive fully intact based on half-life of individual nucleotides.

Assuming independent first-order (exponential) hydrolysis with constant rate k , the survival probability of a single bond for time t is

$$P_{bond}(t) = e^{-kt} \quad (26)$$

A chain of L nucleotides contains $L-1$ independent internucleotide bonds, so the probability that all bonds remain intact is

$$P_{molecule}(t) = (e^{-kt})^{L-1} = e^{-k(L-1)t} \quad (27)$$

The whole-molecule half-life satisfies

$$P_{molecule}(t_{1/2,molecule}) = 1/2 \quad (28)$$

Therefore,

$$e^{-k(L-1)t_{1/2,molecule}} = 1/2 \quad (29)$$

implying that

$$t_{1/2,molecule} = \frac{\ln 2}{k(L-1)} \quad (30)$$

Because $t_{1/2,bond} = \ln 2/k$,

$$t_{1/2,molecule} = \frac{t_{1/2,bond}}{L-1} \quad (31)$$

Appendix 2. Half-lives of glycosidic bond connecting pentose sugar and nucleobase.

In the Arrhenius equation, $k = A \exp(-Ea/RT)$, the pre-exponential factor (frequency factor) A is generally not known, but if a reference value for k is known at a different temperature a linear form can be derived to calculate k at a different temperature.

$$k(T) = A e^{\frac{Ea}{RT}} \quad (32)$$

and

$$k(T_0) = A e^{\frac{Ea}{RT_0}} \quad (33)$$

Taking the ratio and rearranging leads to

$$k(T) = k(T_0) \times e^{\left[-\frac{Ea}{R} \times \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0}\right)\right]} \quad (34)$$

The parameters were taken from Stockbridge *et al.*²⁰

$T_0 = 298.15$ K (for 25 °C)

$T = 363.15$ K (for 90 °C)

$k(25^\circ\text{C}) = 3.7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ s}^{-1}$

$Ea = 28.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1} = 117,152 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$

$R = 8.314462618 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$

The resulting calculated rate constants using eqn. (34) were used to estimate half-lives, using the relationship $t_{1/2} = \ln(2) / k$, with the results shown in table 1.

Table 1. Calculated half-lives of the glycosidic bond connecting RNA ribose and nucleobase, at pH 7. The parameters were taken from Stockbridge *et al.*²⁰

Temperature	Rate constant, k	Half-life	
		days	Years
25 °C	$3.7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ s}^{-1}$	2,168,253	5,936
80 °C	$5.82 \times 10^{-9} \text{ s}^{-1}$	1379.3	3.78
85 °C	$1.02 \times 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$	790.2	2.16
90 °C	$1.75 \times 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$	459.7	1.26
95 °C	$2.96 \times 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$	271.4	0.74
100 °C	$1.40 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-1}$	162.5	0.44

Appendix 3. Montmorillonite to concentrate reactants.

Montmorillonite ((Na, Ca)_{0.33}(Al, Mg)₂(Si₄O₁₀)(OH)₂ · nH₂O) has been extensively studied because amino groups on nucleobases can bind to its surface, facilitating reactions between phosphate and -OH groups on adjacent nucleosides. While 3',5'-dimers formed in its presence (but not its absence), many other products also resulted. For several reasons, conditions used with montmorillonite would not explain the origin of large RNA chains. Examples from the seminal paper include:⁸⁶

- Elaborate protocols removed all organic material that could interfere with reactions.
- The coupling agent EDAC (1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide) used to activate phosphate groups would not exist prebiotically, and was used at extremely high concentrations.
- Alternative minerals like Cu²⁺-montmorillonite that would have also been present showed no catalytic effect.
- Prebiotically plausible activating reagents like diiminosuccinonitrile (DISN) showed no catalytic effect.
- The pure Na⁺-montmorillonite and EDAC were optimally prepared by centrifuging and other measures.
- Very high concentrations of 5'-AMP of 14.5 mM were used.
- The 5'-AMP, Na⁺-montmorillonite and EDAC were thoroughly mixed in a vortex mixer.
- Highest 5',3'-dinucleotide yields occurred at 4°C but decreased rapidly with temperature.

To be an efficient catalyst to form RNA oligomer, montmorillonite is usually pretreated, to ensure the exchangeable cation in the mineral is an alkali or an alkaline earth metal ion.²⁵

All conditions generated far more biologically incorrect 5',2'-dimers than 5',3'-dimers, plus other products. Enhanced dinucleotide yield was a design artifact achieved only by pre-activating phosphate groups and concentrating vast numbers of copies adjacently on montmorillonite where they could react before hydrolyzing.

Subsequent decades saw efforts to improve yields and prebiotic plausibility, typically by converting to imidazolides. A widely cited Science publication reported more promising results using 14.5 mM solutions of 5'-phosphorimidazole adenosine (ImpA) mixed with high concentrations of Na⁺-Volclay for 3 days at room temperature¹⁰⁵

Oligomers up to 10 nucleotides formed, though chains ≥8-mers existed only in trace amounts. Exclusively 3',5'-linked polymers comprised small fractions: 9% of trimers, 3% of tetramers, and 27% of pentamers. These results required carefully designed experiments—rapid vortex mixing brought concentrated nucleosides into contact with charged mineral surfaces for attachment and brought activating agents into contact with phosphate groups, driving polymerization faster than hydrolysis.

Oligomerization of 15 mM ImpA without Na⁺-montmorillonite produced only cyclic dimers and trace linear dimers. With montmorillonite as catalyst, 15 mM ImpA produced oligomers up to 11-mers (in traces), but lowering ImpA to 1.5 mM yielded nothing longer than trimers,

and 0.15 mM ImpA produced only dimers. This trend's importance cannot be overstated, since even 0.15 mM pure ImpA is prebiotically unrealistic.

Kinetic studies indicated montmorillonite enhanced condensation rate constants 100–1000-fold over hydrolysis of the imidazole-activating group.²⁵

Catalysts like montmorillonite generate high local reactant concentrations at catalytic sites within interlayers that facilitate polymerization. However, activated nucleotides hydrolyze rapidly in free water.²⁵

Ferris (2006) summarized recent engineered methods for obtaining longer oligomers.²⁵ Using a "feeding reaction" strategy—adding fresh activated monomer daily to a 10-mer primer already attached to montmorillonite—produced approximately 30–40-mers attached to the primer. Changing the phosphate-activating group from imidazole to 1-methyladenine produced 40–50-mers of A or U without primers.

In another series of experiments, the phosphate-activating group was changed from imidazole to a more complex 1-methyladenine, which produced 40–50-mers of A or U without using a primer.

Montmorillonite is common in deep-sea sediments and acts as an efficient adsorbent. Laboratory procedures optimize insertion of activated nucleosides into interlayer spaces deep within the mineral. However, on ocean bottoms only exterior surfaces of clay aggregates are exposed to potential nucleosides. Laboratory protocols rapidly stirred powdered montmorillonite to greatly increase exposed surface area. When stirring ceased, dispersed clay particles settled under gravity, forcing free water out from between particles. Activated nucleotides attached to clay became locally concentrated in a designed manner, decreasing the magnitude of unfavourable equilibrium constants K in equation (5).

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